

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their counter synthesis, and elemental analysis, m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

The ir spectra of the compounds revealed ν_{\max} 1 650, 1 600 and 1 490 (C=O), 1 420 and 1 240 (C-N), 1 330 (Ar-N) and 750 cm^{-1} (monosubstituted benzene ring); λ_{\max} 331.5 and 293.5 nm, supporting the validity of the compounds.

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde: It was prepared by the reported method⁸.

Malonanilic acid hydrazides: Malonanilic acid hydrazides were prepared in two stages⁴. The amine and diethylmalonate were mixed and heated for 1 h, then cooled and ethanol was added. To the separated ethyl malonanilate dissolved in ethanol, was added hydrazine hydrate (99%) dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture was set aside for 1 h and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol.

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde malonanilic acid hydrazone: A mixture of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) and malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 4 h in ethanol (50 ml). The contents were then cooled, filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	228	70.81
2.	2-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	264	71.98
3.	3-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	211	69.11
4.	4-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	152	70.52
5.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	201	73.97
6.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	215	71.23
7.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄	178	69.86
8.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	210	71.42
9.	3-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	140	67.14
10.	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	185	74.28
11.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	135	70.05
12.	3-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	218	73.35
13.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	270	70.35
14.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	252	71.85
15.	3,4-(OH) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	205	70.40

Biological screening: The compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antitubercular activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *In vitro* antitubercular activity was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *M. tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The retardation of growth was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The antibacterial activity was tested by cup-plate method⁵ using a species of gram (+ve) bacteria *S. aureus* and gram (-ve) bacteria *E. coli* in DMF.

Results and Discussion

Indole-3-carboxaldehyde substituted malonanilic acid hydrazones were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compounds with 3-chloro, 4-chloro, 4-nitro, 3-methoxy, 4-ethoxy, 2-methyl, 4-methyl and 3,4-dimethyl substitution to phenyl ring were active against *S. aureus*. Out of 15 compounds, 8 compounds were active against *S. aureus*, and out of 15 compounds, 5 compounds were active against *E. coli*. Compounds with 3-nitro, 4-methoxy, 3-methyl, 4-methyl and without substitution to phenyl ring were more active against *S. aureus* than *E. coli*. The same compounds when tested for their antitubercular activity, 4-chloro, 4-nitro, 4-methoxy, 4-ethoxy, 4-methyl and 3,4-dimethylphenyl derivatives were found active.

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Studies in Synthesis of Amidoxime. Synthesis of Hexahydro-2H-azepin-2-one Oxime

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REACTION between the carbonyl compounds and hydroxylamine or its salts are known as oximation reactions which have been thoroughly studied and the quantitative methods based on

these reactions are the most extensively used for the determination of an aldehyde or a ketone. Duke¹ suggested that the appearance of the liberated hydrochloric acid, when the carbonyl compounds react with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to form oxime, could be used as a test for the presence of an aldehyde or a ketone. Ample work is reported in literature regarding the oximation reaction on aldehydes and ketones, but very little on the oximation of amide. Lazennec² reported oximation of phenylpropionic amide to give 3-phenyl-5-isoxazolone. Similarly, Spoerri³ showed that the oximation of dicarboxylic acid amides gave hydroxamic acids. In both the cases there is no amidoxime formation. However, Russell⁴ reported amidoxime synthesis from the condensation of thioamides with hydroxylamine. Similar type of work is reported by Hans⁵—amidoxime was prepared through thioamide formation as well as *s*-methyl-lactim formation. Also derivatives of many cyclic amide oximes are reported as fungicide, nematocide and to control wheat and rice leaf rust⁷⁻⁹.

In the present investigation, the synthesis of amidoxime was undertaken with a view to explore the possibility of the direct condensation of amide with hydroxylamine or its salt as well as through *o*-methyl-lactim formation. Hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one oxime (1) was prepared in nearly quantitative yield by reacting tetrahydro-2-methoxyazepine (2) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. 2 was prepared by the condensation of hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one (3) with dimethyl sulphate (Scheme 1). The preparation of 2 is reported^{5,10} in the literature by phosgenation of 3 and subsequently treated with methanol. The structure of 2 was confirmed on the basis of its boiling point^{5,6} and ir spectral data. The ir spectra showed characteristic stretching frequencies at ν_{\max} 1 665 (C=N) and 1 120 and 1 320 cm^{-1} for (C-O). Similarly, the structure of 1 was established by its ¹H nmr and ir spectral data; δ (CDCl₃) 1.5–1.9 (6H, s br, (CH₂)₆ at 4,5,6-positions), 2.2–2.45 (2H, t, not resolved properly and seems to be s br CH₂ at 3-position), 3.1–3.4 (2H, m, not resolved properly and seems to be s br CH₂ at 7-position), 5.45–5.9 (1H, s, =NOH disappeared by D₂O exchange) and 7.95–8.3 (1H, s, N-H which also disappeared by D₂O exchange); 1 660 (C=N), 3 380 and 1 490 (NH), 1 430 and 1 190 for (=C-N) and 3 220 cm^{-1} (OH).

Alternately, hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one (3) was condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in polar solvent like water and methanol directly as well as in presence of a proton acceptor. In both the cases, resulted reaction mass showed deep red colouration with Fe³⁺ salt, confirming the formation of 1. The tlc of the reaction product on silica gel, eluted with toluene-methanol (70 : 30) and visualised by spraying 2% aqueous solution of ferric ammonium sulphate, showed red colouration where the amide oxime spot was present. Attempts to isolate the oxime from the reaction mass failed. Thus it

may be concluded that the oximation of cyclic amide like hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one can be done directly as well as via its methoxy derivative formation, but in the former case the product could not be isolated.

Experimental

The melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 90 Hz instrument. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer IR-577 spectrophotometer.

Tetrahydro-2-methoxyazepine (2): A mixture of 3 (0.1 mol, 11.3 g), dimethyl sulphate purified (0.15 mol, 14.1 ml), anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.15 mol, 16.0 g) and acetone (150 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath with constant stirring for 20 h. The solvent was distilled off and the residue poured into ice-water (250 ml). The product was extracted with chloroform and after drying the extract with anhydrous Na₂CO₃, the solvent was removed by distillation and then under reduced pressure to yield 2 as colourless liquid (2.5 g, 20%), b.p. 52–3°/18.0 mm; ν_{\max} (CCl₄) 1 665 (C=N), 1 120 and 1 310 cm^{-1} (C-O).

Hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one oxime (1): A solution of 2 (2.5 g), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.55 g) and sodium bicarbonate (1.85 g) in methanol (20.0 ml) was stirred and refluxed for 15 h. After removal of the solvent by distillation, the reaction product was poured into water (50 ml) and extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried (anhydrous Na₂CO₃) and the solvent distilled off to get a solid (2.3 g) which was crystallised from acetone to white crystalline leaflets (2.2 g, 87.3%), m.p. 165–65.5° (Found: C, 56.13; H, 9.29; N, 21.80. Calcd. for: C, 56.25; H, 9.38; N, 21.38%); ν_{\max} (2% in KBr) 1 660 (C=N), 3 380 and 1 480 (NH), 1 430 and 1 190 (=C-N) and 3 220 cm^{-1} (OH).

Hexahydro-2*H*-azepin-2-one oxime (1): A mixture of 3 (22.6 g, 0.2 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (15.3 g, 0.22 mol) and water (30.0 ml) was heated upto 90–100° with constant stirring for 25 h. The reaction mixture was neutralised with aqueous 30% NaOH upto 7.0 pH and left overnight. It was then extracted with chloroform. The aqueous layer was concentrated by removal of water under reduced pressure to get a pasty mass. To the latter

was added absolute ethanol (35 ml) and the separated solid NaCl was removed by filtration. Ethanol was removed from the filtrate under the reduced pressure to get very thick oily pale yellow product (31.7 g) containing 15.4% water (by Karl Fischer); it showed deep red colouration with 2.0% aqueous ferric ammonium sulphate solution. The solid **1** could not be isolated in pure form.

Hexahydro-2H-azepin-2-one oxime (1): A solution of **3** (11.3 g, 0.1 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6.95 g, 0.1 mol) and NaHCO₃ (8.4 g, 0.1 mol) in 90% aqueous methanol (25 ml) was refluxed with constant stirring for 30 h. The reaction mass was cooled and filtered. From the filtrate, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get a pale yellow viscous oil (13.6 g) which showed deep red colouration with 2.0% aqueous ferric ammonium sulphate solution. The viscous oil was contained 6.25% water (by Karl Fischer). Compound **1** could not be isolated in pure form.

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Addition-Elimination Reactions of 4- and 6-Chloroindolin-2,3-diones with certain Nucleophilic Reagents†

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INDOLIN-2, 3-dione and 5,7-substituted-indolin-2,3-dione have been conveniently prepared via Sandmeyer isonitroso synthesis¹. The 3-carbonyl group in indolin-2,3-diones behaves normally

† Dedicated to Prof. W. Pfeleiderer, Universität Konstanz, West Germany on his 60th. birthday, July 22, 1987.

towards nucleophilic reagents and as such numerous addition-elimination reactions have been performed leading to the 3-substituted products²; many such products have shown interesting biological activity³. While nucleophilic reactions on indolin-2,3-diones and 5,7-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones have been reported, not much work has been done on 4- and/or 6-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones, the reason might be the difficulty in getting pure 4- and/or 6-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones via Sandmeyer method. We have now obtained 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones in a pure state by a pH-dependent separation procedure from their mixture⁴.

Nucleophilic attack of benzoic acid hydrazides on **4** and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (**1a**, **b**) underwent smoothly leading to the formation of **4a** and **4d** in excellent yields. **1a** and **1b** were treated with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic KOH to get the corresponding 1-methyl analogs which were again treated with benzoic acid hydrazides yielding **3a** and **3b**, respectively. Further, Mannich condensation on **4a** and **4b** resulted in the formation of 1-morpholino/piperidino-(methyl-4/6-chloro)-3-(benzoylhydrazano)-2-indolinones (**5a** and **5b**) (Scheme 1). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir and pmr spectral data.

Scheme 1. Reagents. (i) Me₂SO, /KOH-EtOH, (ii) o/p-substituted-benzoylhydrazones, (iii) morpholine/piperidine/HCHO.

The ir spectra of **3-5** showed characteristic bands at 3 150 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 665 (C=O amide) and 1 615 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The pmr spectrum of **5a** sl. no. 11 (Table 1) showed resonance at δ 3.57 (4H, N (CH₂)₂), 4.02 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 5.2 (2H, NCH₂N) and 7-7.9 (7H, ArH) which is in conformity with the assigned structure.